

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	ZHY-1-27-IG-5% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	14	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	ZHY 1 27
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/17/2022 10:13:12 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 8:53:01 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.567	764422	49.92	73174
2	8.147	767002	50.08	54785

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-131-IG-5% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	15	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 131
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/18/2022 17:19:18 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 20:43:55 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.455	4684028	97.13	450122
2	7.945	138323	2.87	10189